

Determinants of Commercialization of Smallholder Red Papper Farmers in Javietenan District, Amahara Region, Ethiopia

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to analysis the determinants of commercialization red papper. Particularly, the study investigate the level of commercialization of red pepper production, and factors that affect household participation in the red papper out put market. Simple random sampling was applied to select sample kebeles and the 214 sample respondents were selected based on simple random sampling technique from the five sample kebeles. Structured questioner was a main tool to collect cross sectional data from the sample respondents.. The descriptive analysis revealed that the level of commercialization in the study area was on average semi commercial one. Moreover, one way ANOVA test was applied to cheek the existence of significant total factor productivity variation among households operating at different levels of commercialization. Censured Tobit regression was applied to analysis the factors that affect market participation of households' in red papper output market. The result revealed that from the total 12 explanatory variables, five variables were statistically significant. Of which, land size (land allocated for red papper production) and previous year market price of red papper was positively related with market participation and while participation in the off farm income activities, access to credit service from formal financial institution and educational level of the household heads related negatively with quantity or volume of teff sold. Thus, emphasis and intervention should be given for household to increase market participation and improve levels of commercialization.

Keyword:- Commercialization, Households, Red Papper, Factor Productivity, Market Participation.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the study

The Ethiopia economy experience mainly three economic sectors .these are agriculture, manufacturing and service sectors. From these, agriculture sector plays a vital role for employment creation, foreign exchange generation, means of income and livelihoods. According to (CSA, 2007/2014), the agriculture sectors provide 83% of employment from the total population and constitute for more than 50% of gross domestic product (GDP) growth for the country.

Even though agriculture sector entitle various benefit, but the practice and performance has been characterized as smallholder farming and subsistence. This means the agriculture activity conducted through inhering of family labor, the labor to land ratio is too high and few degree of specialization. Thus, lower productivity, lower income and lower standard of living are common. Furthermore; smallholding farming is a means for life sustenance (Goitom, 2009).

Households aiming to reduce poverty, to achieve for sustainable food security, maximize welfare and to improve livelihood, subsistence agriculture must be structured /shifted to commercialization (Pingali, 1997).

Different countries and worldwide development agencies puts critical focus on smallholder farming intensification and commercialization aiming to reduce poverty and suggest direction to countries exercise in their official policy (Leave and pouiton, 2007).

To integrate farm households in to market, different activities are curried out from 1950s up to now .during 1950s the major concern were improving productivity and reducing economic dependency on subsistence agriculture and in 1960s the focus were developing agro industry economy and increments in foreign earning. After the derg regime come to power, the major attempts were adopting socialism economy and the current government strongly concerned on smallholder farming, poverty reduction and promote intensification of agriculture (sharp et al, 2007).

Commercialization in agriculture refers to the progressive shift from household production for auto-consumption to production for sale in the market. This shift entails that production and input decisions are based on profit maximization, reinforcing vertical linkages between input and output markets (Olwande *et al.*, 2015).

It is obvious that, commercialization is long run process that farming shifts from subsistence (non commercial) to semi-commercial farming, and then to fully commercialized agriculture. In the case of open market economy, commercialization of agriculture enables to welfare gains for farmers through comparative advantage and increased total factor productivity growth (Pingali and Rosegrant, 1995).

Increase the extent of commercialization of farming among Sub-Saharan Africa's generally semi-subsistence, low-input, low-productivity smallholder farmers have seen as playing a significant role in poverty alleviation (Olwande *et al.*, 2015).

Commercializing smallholder agriculture has seen as a means to bring the welfare benefits of market-based exchange economies, and is central to an inclusive development process (Arias *et al.*, 2013).

Commercialization has been advanced as a means of improving smallholder farmers' income and reducing rural poverty in many developing countries and it has also been considered as a major strategy of ensuring household food security (WDR, 2008).

For subsistence agriculture, commercialization may not be the whole process and that involves the importance of equity issue. Moreover, smallholder farmers excluded from the benefit of commercialization practice this is because lowers access for infrastructure and service and the existence of transaction cost emanate from newly emerging market organizations. Besides to this the change in the economic development brings the increment of per capita income, progress in technology use and urbanization that leads the change of food marketing in developing nations (Reardon and Timmer, 2007).

Since 2005 the government of Ethiopia gives strong prioritization for commercialization of farming in the development agenda. According to MoFED (2006) commercialization of agriculture, based on the support of intensification of marketable farm outputs for domestic and foreign market by both small and large scale farmers and encourage off farm private sectors growth.

Growth and transformation plan of Ethiopia focused on meeting the MDGs goal through rising crop production by adopting better farming practice, increase cultivated agriculture land, improve extension service utilization and agriculture inputs. Moreover rural development strategy intended to contribute to the transformation of productive rural sector from primary subsistence to more market oriented sectors, contribute to the overall growth and poverty reduction (sharp *et al.*, 2007).

Pepper is the world's second important agricultural vegetable product ranking after tomatoes and it is the most produced type of spice which used as a fresh vegetable in salads and sandwiches, and as a cooked vegetable for a wide variety of dishes throughout the world. It also contains more vitamin C to prevent flu colds than any other vegetable crop (Acquaah, 2004, Rudrappa, 2016).

The pepper origin is around Central and South America. Peru and Mexico might have been also the second centers of origin, before its subsequent introduction into Asia and Africa in 1493 (Bosland and Votava, 2000). Pepper has given different name in different countries of the Asia. la-jiao in China, cabe in Indonesia, prik in Thailand, and chilli in India.

The early Aztecs of Mexico also called them chilli, and this term is the most commonly used today around the world, with some variant spellings: chile, chili, chilly, etc (Berke, 2002). According to American Spice Trade Association (ASTA), red pepper is preferred name for all hot red pepper and now it is produced in all the continents except Antarctica (EEPA, 2013).

Pepper is also a national spice of Ethiopia and believed to be introduced to Ethiopia probably by the Portuguese in the 17th century (Hafnagel, 1961). The history of pepper in Ethiopia is perhaps the most ancient than the history of any other vegetable product and it has been cultivated in many parts of the country because it is the daily diet of most Ethiopian people and Ethiopian adult average daily consumption of hot pepper is estimated around 15 gram, which is better than tomato and other vegetables (MARC, 2004).

In Ethiopia, pepper is cultivated in many parts of the country. Areas like western Gojjam (Jabitehinan, Burie and Shindi districts), eastern and southern Shewa, western and northwestern Wellega, and the southern Ethiopia (Alaba and the Mareko) are potential producers of pepper in Ethiopia.

According to CSA, (2020/21), the estimated production of red peppers in quintals at the national level, in the Amhara Region, West Gojjam zone and in the jabithenan woreda were 3,298,042.90, 1,161,185.52, 574,219.78 and 224721.5 respectively but the share Ethiopia in the world is insignificant. Compared to India that produced 40 million quintal from 891,800 hectare in 1992, Ethiopia's production in 2016/17 was only 3,298,042.90 quintal harvested on 180,701.46 hectares (CSA, 2020/21).

B. Statements of Problem

Overcoming the challenge of improved rural income in Africa require some form of transformation out of semi subsistence, low productivity farming system and low income that currently characterize rural Africa (Govereh, 1999).

The developing country especially sub saharan countries agricultural markets are characterised by poorly functioning markets, low investment in the market infrastructure, farmers are not getting the right share of consumer price because of inefficient and costly transport, limited access to technological innovation, and market information and weak commodity value chains still hinder smallholder farmers' full access to markets (Eleni 2001).

In order to make agriculture the engine of growth, there has to be a progress in terms of commercialization with more intense farming and increasing the proportion of market supply. But, despite the effort and emphasis given to agriculture the observation achievements' are not satisfactory (kefyalew, 2010). In addition, above 85 % of Ethiopia's the population are depends on agriculture and largely characterized by subsistence farming. Smallholder farmers operating on by most estimates, an average of one hectare, account for about 95% of agricultural output (Pender *et al.*, 2004).

According to mahlet (2007), smallholder farmers cultivate 95% of total crop land and produce around 95 % of agricultural outputs. Besides agriculture sectors generates 90% of foreign exchange earnings. This indicates that Ethiopia economy is dominantly subsistence and non commercial.

The Ethiopia government prepares plan and strategy in the development policy agenda in order to transform subsistence farming to commercial one .To do so; agriculture development led industrialization (ADLI) policy have been in practice since 1994. This policy integrate various ingredient that promote the growth of agriculture such as finance, market integrations (internal and external), private investment, rural infrastructures and technology .The focus of this policy has been commercialization of agriculture, provide access to credit service for stallholder farmers, improve food security and industrialization (Sharp et al 2007).

But the reality behind commercialization of smallholder farming currently is not too enough for farmer to benefit from income increase and to escape from subsistence oriented agriculture due to the agriculture sector is highly dominated by small scale subsistence agriculture and low productive (Birhanu and Moti, 2010) and also the occurrence of market imperfection and high transaction cost hinders smallholders not to enjoy and benefit welfare from commercialization unless better environment is created (Bernand et al, 2007).

Growth and transformation plan (GTP) of Ethiopia was aimed to increase productivity of dominant crops through good agricultural practice .Since poverty reduction strategy seeks growth that combine commercialization of smallholder agriculture (MoFED, 2010).

Samuel and sharp (2007) noted that four categories that represent potential complementary pathways for commercialization policy in Ethiopia. These are smallholder farmers (subsistence), small holder farm(market oriented), small investor farms and large scale agro business .on average around 11.5 million Ethiopia farmers are found under the smallholder subsistence and smallholder market oriented (MoFED,2006). Likewise majorities of farmer who are engaged in red paper production of BURIE Worreda are characterized under the categories of subsistence small farming and market oriented smallholder.

The study area is well-known in the production of different staple food crops that are grown at different agro ecological zones such as teff, maize, wheat, barley, sorghum, chickpea, and beans “guaya” and various fruits and vegetables. From this, Teff are the most dominant crops for the farm households and the area ranked 12th from 25 major teff growing area in Ethiopia (James et al, 2015). Now the principal motive for researcher interested to deal with teff is that, it is the most marketed and highly demanded both cash and food crops in the studying area. But there is still unsatisfied demand in the market since the supply of teff is mainly seasonal. That implies farmers sold teff during the

harvest season and rarely at summer to purchase agricultural inputs.

Cognizant of this fact, commercialization of teff that enhance productivity, food security, poverty reduction and rise of income can be affected by different socio- economic, political, environmental and institutional factors. Accordingly, commercialization can be affected both locally and internationally. Locally, it is affected by input marker, institution, consumption preference, culture, and price, level of production, infrastructures and access to information. But at the international levels, commercialization also affected by international trade, globalization, population growth, urbanization, growth of different economic sectors and infrastructure (Pender et al, 2007).

There are related literatures on commercialization of smallholder agriculture. For instance Goitom,(2009) in his study commercialization of smallholder farming indicates that the role of commercialization on household welfare and measure household participation in the output market by using multiple linear regression. likewise, Samuel and Sharp(2007) in their study commercialization of smallholder agriculture in selected teff growing area in Ethiopia also measure household participation in the output market two stage least square method . But this method simply shows the linear relationship between market participation and other explanatory variables. Therefore, the researcher determine households participation in the output market by using **Tobit regression** models since the output variable can censored in to commercial(high participant) , semi commercial(medium participant and subsistent(low participant).Moreover, the researcher adds access to training and access to extension service as a new independent variable that is not considered by former researchers.

Finally the researcher is interested to deal with commercialization of teff since there is no scientific and systematic research work conducted in the study area by the title with determinant of commercialization of teff and its factor productivity outcomes. Therefore, the researcher likes to clearly show the issue of level of commercialization, factor that determine households participation in the teff market and how factor productivity influence households operating at level of commercialization in the studying area.

C. Objectives of the Study

➤ The General Objective

The general objective of the study is to explore the determinant of commercialization of red papper and its factor productivity outcomes in the case of burie Worreda, Amahara region Ethiopia.

➤ Specific Objective of the Study

These are the specific objectives that support to answers the general objective.

- To examine the current levels of commercialization of red papper production in the studying area
- To measure total factor productivity outcomes at the different levels of commercialization

- To analysis the factor that affect households participation in the red papper output market

D. Basic Research Questions

The researcher puts the following basic research question to give feedback for the stated specific problems. These are:

- What is the current level of commercialization of red papper production in the study area?
- What measure the total factor productivity outcomes that could influence commercialization at different levels?
- What determine household participation in red papper output market?

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Description of the study Area

This research was conducted in Jabi Tehinan woreda of west Gojam Zone located in the Amhara National Regional State. Jabi Tehinan is one of the 15 woredas of West Gojjam administrative zone. It is found 374 kms Northwest of Addis Ababa and 171.7 kms south west of Bahir Dar, the Regional State capital.

The woreda covers a total of 117,020 hectares. Currently, the woreda is divided in to 37 rural Kebele administrations (KAs) and 3 towns Finote Selam, Mankusa and Jiga are the major towns in the woreda. According to the woreda BOARD (2016/17) report, human population of the woreda is 270,147 of which 253,348 live in rural areas while the rest 16,799 live in urban areas. The climate of the woreda is in general 88% Weina Dega and 12% Kola. The average annual rainfall of the woreda is 1250 mm. The Western and Northern parts of the woreda receive relatively higher rainfall compared to other parts of the woreda. The woreda has mono-modal rainfall distribution and extends from May to September pepper, Maize, teff and wheat are the major crop in the woreda (BoARD, 2016/17). Topographically, the woreda is classified as plain land (65%), terrain (15%), valley (15%) and unclassified land (5%). Altitude of the woreda ranges from 1300 to 2300 masl. The mean annual temperature ranges from 14oC to 32oC. Three soil types, namely black (15%), red (60%) and brown (25%) are predominant in the woreda. When the soil fertility is considered, it is classified as 27% fertile, 71% of medium fertile and 2% degraded land (BoARD, 2009). Given the above, information is an important force that makes assessment of the value chain of red pepper in the woreda more crucial.

B. Data Type and Source

Data is important inputs that enable researchers to conduct research and solve specific societal problems. The nature of the research determine the types of data (cross sectional or time series) required by the researchers. To conduct the study, the researcher would use cross sectional data types since it covers a point at a time. Besides, the nature data that would be used is only quantitative data.

The other important part of this section is data source .The researcher would use both primary and secondary source of data in order to carry out the study. Primary data is fresh and first hand data and would obtains from rural household survey of **jabiethenan** woreda .

C. Data collection procedure:

Data can be collected by different procedures such as; questionnaire (structured vs. non structured), interview, direct observation, key informant interview and focus group discussion (FGD) and others. For this study, to collect the desired data, the researcher applied mainly structured questionnaires that would be distributed for the sample rural households.

D. Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

➤ *Sampling procedure (technique):*

It is important to identify the appropriate respondents so as to undertake the study. Basically there are two types of sampling technique which have been applied in research work that is probability and non probability sampling procedure. The researcher would apply only probability sampling technique which is two stage sampling.

A two-stage sampling design was employed in order to select sample unit. In the first stage five major kebeles were select purposively based level of producing potential and second stage among households that exist five kebele will select using Proportionate random sampling technique was use to decide numbers of sample from each kebele.

➤ *Sample size*

According to C.R Kothari (2004), the representative sample size must be optimum. This means samples should neither be too large nor too small. Therefore, so as to determine the optimum level of sample in any study, researchers must consider the following four prominent factors such as: level of confidence (α), margin of error (e), variability of the population(s) and the number of groups within the samples. Moreover, method of analysis, objective of research, cost, and time determine the type and size of the sample to be employed. Agriculture and rural development office of buie woreda report reveals that the total numbers of population for the woreda at the household levels are 6794.. For finite population, the best sample size determination have been used Yamane (1967). Generally the model can be specified as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (1)}$$

Where n is sample size which target population is less than 10000

N is population size which is 6794

e is the level precision i.e. the level confidence limit is 93%

$$n = \frac{6794}{1+6794(0.07^2)} = 204.02$$

The overall sample size of the survey will also increase by 5% for non-response. $204.02 \times 5\% = 10.20$. Hence, the total sample size of the study will be, $204.02 + 10.20 = 214.22 \cong 214$

Hence, 214 respondents from five Kebeles of the woreda household will be selected based on proportionate random sampling technique

E. Methods of Data Analysis

So as to analyze the collected data, the researcher has used both descriptive and econometrics analysis.

➤ *Descriptive analysis*

This ways of data analysis is important to explain or illustrate demographic and socio economic variables by using maximum, minimum, mean and standard deviation. For this research, to answer the first (levels of commercialization) and the second specific objectives, descriptive analysis has applied.

The first specific objective of the study is determining the levels of commercialization of red papper in the study area. According to Govern et al (1999) and Strasberg et al (1999), level of commercialization at household level can be measured as the ratio of gross value of all crops sold in a year per gross value of all out put produced by the same year. Since this study only concerned on red papper, household level commercialization can be drown as follow:

$$\text{Household commercialization index (HCI)} = \frac{\text{gross value of teff sold by hh inthe markrt}}{\text{gross value of teffproduced by hh}} \times 100$$

Based on the commercialization index developed above, the value ranged between 0 and 100%. Thus, If the HCI become zero, the household is subsistence or not commercial. But if it is approached to 100% it is commercialized. Leavy and polton (2007) also have developed the three fundamental levels of commercialization as subsistence (non commercial), semi commercial and highly commercial. For this study, levels of commercialization can be also categorized into three based on the cut off developed by (Goitom , 2009 and Salisu et al., 2017) as:

- Non commercial(low level) - if the households sale less than 25% of output they produced
- Semi commercial(medium levels)- if the households sale b/n 26% -50% of output they produced
- Highly commercial(high levels) – if the households sale above 50% of output they produced

The second objective of the study is about total factor productivity outcome which varies across different levels of commercialization. Total factor productivity encourages agricultural development and increase market sale (Rios et al, 2009). Tornqvist TFP index has been used to measure factor productivity outcomes. That implies it is the ratio output commercialization index per input commercialization index multiplied by hundred. Basically total factor productivity includes land, labor, capitals, fertilizers, special seeds and

pest sides. Generally, tornqvist TFP index can be modeled in logarithm form as follow:

$$\ln TFP = \ln \frac{o}{I} = \ln o - \ln I ; \text{ Where, } o = \text{output index, } I = \text{input index and TFP} = \text{total factor productivity. Moreover, total factor productivity index enables to show the difference in output across groups. For this study, to measure factor productivity outcomes of teff in the sample household that operate at different levels of commercialization, One Way ANOVA (analysis of variance) has been used. One way ANOVA analysis is important to compare the mean of the sample or groups to make inference about the population mean. The basic assumptions of one way ANOVA analysis is equal mean of population (Independence).$$

➤ *Econometrics Analysis*

The third specific objective of the study is about factor that affects household participation in the teff market. This objective requires econometric analysis to examine the relationship and impact of explanatory variables on outcome variable. The dependent variable for this study is market participation of households in the red papper market. It is the ratio of gross value of output sold per gross value of all output produced multiplied by one hundred and its valve ranged between zero and one.

Therefore, market participation of households can be determined by using censured Tobit regression models since the dependent variable is censured from true zero value. According to Tobin (1958), the general form of the model can be specified as follow:

$$Y_i = \beta X_i + \epsilon_i \dots \dots \dots \text{from this equation,}$$

$Y_i \leq 0 \dots \dots$ For households don't participate in the market (zero sales)

$Y_i > 0 \dots \dots$ For household do participate in the market

Where: Y_i = the limited dependent variable, represent index of market participation

X_i = vectors of explanatory variables

B_i = vectors of unknown parameters

ϵ_i = represent the disturbance term

$i = 1, 2 \dots n$ (numbers of possible observation)

F. Assumption Tobit regression model

The Tobit regression model basically holds the basic assumption of ordinary least square regression model. To meet fitness of goodness of the models, different econometrics assumption of the models must be checked. The most common assumptions are:

➤ *No or little multicolluniarity:*

This assumption implies that there shouldn't be relationships among the explanatory variables each other. Or independent variables should be independent of each other. This assumption could checked with different techniques such as; variance inflated factor (VIF), correlations matrix and condition index. Under correlation matrix method, the Pearson correlation coefficient must be less than 0.08. Moreover, under condition index, the value must be not more than 30(10-30 value are accepted). The most frequently used

detection technique was VIF. In this method, the value of VIF for each variables must be not more than 10 and the mean VIF less than 2. Therefore, for this study there is no multicollinearity problems since the mean VIF is 1.25 and VIF of each variables is less than 10 (see appendix E).

➤ *Heteroscedasticity:*

This problem is basically happened when the variance of the error term is not constant for observations. This test is important to check the classical linear regression assumption of the error term has constant variance. To know the existence of this problem, the most common method used was Breusch- pagan /cook- Weisberg test. Under this test, the null hypothesis holds constant variance. So, if this hypothesis is rejected, the problem of heteroscedasticity is existed. Moreover, the p value must be greater than 0.05. Therefore, in this study the p value is prob > chi2 =0.07. This indicates that there is no problem existed. (see appendix D).

➤ *Normality:*

It assumes that all variables must be normal and tested with histogram and a fitted normal curve plot. Moreover, it would be check with goodness of fitness. Thus, the kernel density distribution revealed that there was almost normal distribution (see appendix F).

G. Hypothesis and Variable Definition

➤ *Dependent variable:*

The outcome variable for this study is market participation of households in the red papper market. It is a categorical variable and grouped as low participant (subsistent), medium participant (semi commercial) and high participant (commercial).

➤ *Explanatory variables:*

The researcher specifies the most important explanatory variables that affect household participation in the red papper market. These are:

➤ *Age of the household head:*

Basically age is a continuous variable it can be measured with number of years. It measure farmers' experience and attitude towards risk. According to chalachew et, al (2011), having sound experience and wise utilization of inputs at the older age positively affect households participation in output market. Moreover, as attitude towards risk become higher, age of the households negatively affect output sold. Therefore, it may affect positively or negatively.

➤ *Family size:*

It is a continuous variable that indicates the total number of individuals live under the household. The higher the number of the family size, the higher the consumption demand and the lower in participation of sell (Birhanu and Dirk, 2007). Thus, it is expected to affect market participation of households in the red papper market negatively.

➤ *Education levels of household head:*

It is a categorical variable that can be grouped into five different levels. According to Goitom (2009), households with higher education level can have better access to information and easily understand the market. Thus, education would affect market participation of households in the red papper market positively.

➤ *Land size (% Of land allocated for red papper):*

It is a continuous variable that measures the total land holding size allocated for red papper production in hectares. Farmers with more hectares of land holding have high crop diversification. As a result, households' integration in to the output market becomes higher (Pingali, 1995). Thus, land size would affect market participation of households in the red papper market positivity.

➤ *Access to irrigations:*

It is a dichotomous variable and measured as one for households who are participating in irrigation practice and zero otherwise. Irrigation practice can increase crop production in the off season by producing more than once at the fiscal year. (Chanyalew et al, 2011). Thus, access to irrigation would affect market participation of households in the papper market positively.

➤ *Access to credit service:*

It is dichotomous variable that can be measure as one for the households that have access to formal credit and zero otherwise. Access to credit strength financial capacity of households to buy different modern agricultural inputs and this improve productivity (Dawit and Pender, 2007). Therefore, it may affects market participation of households in the red papper market positively.

➤ *Access to extension service:*

It is a dummy variable that express the contact of households with experts. It represents as one for the household that has access to extension service and zero otherwise. The farmers that have access to extension service have better information and integrate modern technology in their production. Moreover, it increases experience or knowledge about commercialization (Goitom, 2009). Therefore extension service expected to affect market participation of households in the red papper market positively.

➤ *Access to training service:*

It reflects the access of training given for farmers during the production period. Moreover, it is dummy variable and represent by one for households that participate in training and zero otherwise. Training service enhances the farmer to fill the gap about technique of production, input usage and adopt new technology (Chanyalew et al, 2011). Therefore, it would expect to affect market participation of households in the red papper market positively.

➤ *Distance from the market:*

It is continuous variable that represents how many kilometers do the farmers travel to reach the nearest market center. The nearest to the center, the lowest transport and information cost expense. Moreover, it reduces the time spent. This enables the farmers to sell more of it (Adam, 2009). Hence, it might market participation of households in the red papper market negatively.

➤ *Livestock size:*

It is also a continuous variable that measures the total amount of livestock the households holding. Farmers with more livestock holding have alternative income source with sale of this livestock and this reduce the sale of crops (Birhanu and Moti, 2010). Therefore, livestock size would expect to affect market participation of households in the red papper market negatively.

➤ *Participation in off farm income:*

It is a dummy variable which measures participation of farmers outside the farming practice. Households that participate in the off farm activity represented by one and zero otherwise. It provides extra income and this enable to invest off farm earning to foster production and sales (Edward,

2013). Thus, it influences market participation of households in the red papper market positively.

➤ *Access to market information:*

It is a dummy variable which can be nominate as one if the households have access to market and zero otherwise. Market information influence decision making households through providing information about price, demand and supply of outputs (Chanyalew et al, 2011). Thus, access to market information would expect to affect market participation of households in the red papper market positively.

➤ *Market Price of red papper:*

It is a continuous variable that could be measured with birr and take previous year average price of teff. When the price of the previous year higher, households supplies more and encouraged to increase production (Edward, 2013).

Therefore, it would expect to affect market participation of households in the red papper market positively.

The following table shows that the summary of variables.

Variables	Types	Measurement	Expected sign
Market participation of households in the red papper market	continuous	ratio	
Age of the head	Continuous	Years	+/-
Education levels	Categorical	1= illiterate, 2, = read and write only,3= 1-4 grade ,4= 5-8 grade, 5 = 9-12and above	+
Access to credit	Dummy	1 for user and 0 otherwise	+
Access to extension	Dummy	1 for user and 0 otherwise	+
Access to training	Dummy	1 for trainer and 0 otherwise	+
Access to market information	Dummy	1 for informed and 0 otherwise	+
Access to irrigation	Dummy	1 for user and 0 otherwise	+
Distance from the market	Continuous	Kilometer	-
Participation on off farm income	Dummy	1 for participant and 0 for non participant	+
Land allocated for red papper	Continuous	Hectares	+
Family size	Continuous	Numbers	-
Livestock size	Continuous	Tropical livestock units	-
Market price of red papper (last year)	Continuous	Birr	+

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Demographic characteristics of the households

This part of the research basically contains the description of demographic variables such as religion, sex, age, educational level and marital status with in the form table and the result expressed with percentage.

Table 1: religion status of the household based on sex

Sex	Christian	Muslim
Male	144 (65.45%)	13 (5.9%)
Female	62 (28.18%)	1 (0.47%)
Total	206 (93.63%)	14(6.37%)

Source: Based on own survey data 2018

From the above table, the researcher can draw that from the total sample households, ninety four (93.63%) the respondents are Christians. of which, 65.45% of the respondents are male household and the remaining 28.18% are female heads. On the other hand, Muslim heads are very small in number and they account just only 6.37%. Of which, there is only 0.47% of female head and the remaining 5.9% are male heads. Now we can conclude Christian households are the most dominant which is 15.5 time higher than the Muslim households. Regarding to sex, 71% of the respondents are males and the remaining 29% are female heads.

Table 2: educational levels of the households based on sex

Educational levels	Male		Female	
	frequency	percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	38	17%	34	16%
Read and write only	61	28%	24	11%
1-4 grade	39	18%	5	2%
5-8 grade	13	5%	-	
9-12 and above	6	3%	-	
Totals	157	71%	63	29%

Source: survey of 2018.

Table 2 explains the relationship between educational levels and sex status of sample households. From the table, 33% of sample respondents are illiterate .of which, 17% are male heads and 16% are female heads. The second category of educational levels of households is writing and read only. It covers the higher percent of the respondents, which is 39%. Of which, 28% of are male and 11% are female heads. Moreover, 20% of the respondents have educational levels of 1-4 grades. From this, 18% of the respondents are male heads and the remaining 2% are female heads. The other categories of educational levels of the households are 5-8 grade and 9-12 and above .within this class of categories, only male household heads are existed. That is 5 % of male heads under 5-8 grade and 3% are 9-12 and above grade. Generally, from the table the researcher can conclude female household heads have little record in the formal education as compared with male heads and only 2% of the female respondents have formal education levels. Moreover, from the total sample households, only 28 % of the respondents have formal educational levels. But the remaining 72% of the sample households are categorized under illiterate and write and read only levels. The average educational levels of the households were read and write only.

Table 3: Marital status of the sample households

Marital status of the households	Numbers of respondents		Totals
	male	Female	
Single	12	4	16 (7%)
Married	135	23	158 (72%)
Divorced	9	22	31 (14%)
Windowed	1	14	15 (7%)
Total	220 (100%)		

Source: based on own survey data 2018.

Marital status of the respondents is another demographic variable that describe households as single, married, divorced and windowed. From the above table, 7% of the respondents are single and 72% of the respondents are also married. The remaining 14% and 7% of the respondents are divorced and windowed respectively. From the table, the researcher also concludes that most of the sample households are married than the other categories.

B. Socio economic characteristics of households

➤ *Access to credit:*

Access to credit from formal financial institution is very important variable that enables the households to have others source of incomes and strength the financial capacity of the households to purchase different inputs. From the total respondents, 28.18% are credit user from formal financial institutions. The following table explains use of credit service from formal financial institution by the household heads.

Table 4 access to credit based on sex of the household

Access to credit	Males respondents	Females respondents	Totals
User	42 (19.09%)	20 (9.09%)	62 (28.18%)
Non user	115 (52.27%)	43 (19.01%)	158 (71.82%)

Source: Based on own survey data 2018

The above table shows that the access to credit service from the formal financial institutions based on sex of the households. Now from the total sample households, 28.18 % are user of credit service. Of which, 19.09% of the respondents are male heads and the remaining 9.09% are female heads. On the other hand, 71.82 % the sample respondents have no access to credit service (non user). From this, 52.27% are male heads and the remaining 19.01% are female heads. Generally, the researcher possibly concludes that, the habit of the use of credit service from the formal financial institution relatively low since user are twice less than from non user .moreover , based on sex male household heads are non user as compare to females .

➤ Access to market information

Market information reduces transaction cost. On average, 40.45 % of the respondents have access to market information .The following table shows households access to market information to sale the red papper out put to the nearest market.

Table 5. Access to market information of the household heads

Access to market information	Frequency	Percentages
Non informed	131	59.54%
Informed	89	40.45%
Totals	220	100

Source: Based on own survey data 2018

The above table indicates that, from the total sample respondents, 59.54% the respondents have no access to market information and the remaining 40.45% of the respondents have access to market information to sales their red papper output in the market. Generally, the non informed are larger from the informed one by almost.

➤ Access to training and extension service

Table: 6 accesses to training service of the sample households

Access to training service	Frequency	Percentage
User	100	45.45%
Non user	120	54.55%
Total	220	100%

Source: Based on own survey data 2018

Training service is crucial for households to share knowledge, technologies and experience that minimize their gaps. As it shown from the above table 6, on average, 45.45% of sample respondents are user of training service and 54.55 % of the respondents are non user of the training service.

Table 7: access to extension service of the sample households

Access to extension service	Frequency	Percentage
User	139	63.13%
Non user	81	36.87%
Totals	220	100%

Source: Based on own survey data 2018

This table conveys the use of agricultural extension service by sample households. Agricultural extension service helps the farm households to used modern inputs like special seed, fertilizers, and pesticides. Moreover, it helps the household to grow market oriented output through improving their awareness. From the table 7, the researcher concludes that, on average, 63.13% of the sample households are benefited from agricultural extension service .whereas, the remaining 36.87% of the respondents are non user of agricultural extension service. This implies that user of agricultural extension service are greater than by almost by half from non user.

➤ *Participation in off farm activity*

Off farm activities are economic activities which are done out of agricultural activities as a means of generating additional income source.

Table 8: participation in the off farm activity based on agro ecology zone

Off farm activity	Agro ecology zone			
	Woynadega zone	Dega zone	Kola zone	Totals
Participant	56 (25.45%)	11 (5%)	18(8.18%)	85(38.63%)
Non participant	82 (37.27%)	31 (14.09%)	22(10%)	135 (61.37%)
Totals	138 (62.72%)	42 (19.09%)	40 (18.18%)	220 (100%)

Source: Based on own survey 2018

From the above mentioned table 8, the participation of households in the off farm activities are on average 38.63% from the total sample households. But the remaining 61.37 % of sample respondents are non participant on the off farm activities. With regarding to agro ecological zone, 62.72% of the respondents are live in woyna dega zone. From this, 25.45% of the households are participant in the off farm activities and the rest 37.27% are non participant. The other agro ecological zone is dega zone. It covers 19.09 % from the total respondents. Of which, only 5% are participant in the off farm activities and 14.09% of the respondents are non participant. Lastly, kola zone covers 18.18 % from the total respondents' .likewise, 10% of respondents in the kola zone are non participant and the remaining 8.18% are participants. Generally, the percentage of non participant in each agro ecological zone is greater than from participant in each agro ecological zone.

➤ *Access to irrigation*

It is the practice of growing agricultural output in addition to the normal production season. It is important to produce output more than one times.

Table 9: access to irrigation of the households

Access to irrigation	Frequency	Percentage
Participant	71	32.27%
Non participant	149	67.73%
Totals	220	100%

Source: based on own survey data 2018

From the table mentioned above, the participation of households in the irrigation activity is lower by half from the non participant. On average, 32.27% of the sample respondents are participant in the irrigation activities. On other hand, 67.73% of the respondents are non participant in the irrigation activities.

Table 10: summary of presentation of continues explanatory variables

Variables	Obs	Means	Std.dev	Min	Max
Agehh	220	49.42727	10.78047	26	75
Distance	220	4.105455	3.016646	1	6.5
Fasize	220	3.922727	1.15408	2	7
Livsize	220	6.266136	3.327429	1.7	18
Pyprice	220	1803.568	33.30871	1700	1900
Lansize	220	2.505682	1.274406	0.5	6

A. Source: based on own survey data 2018

Age is socio economic and demographic variable the express the sample households. The summary of the table indicates that, the maximum age of the respondent is 75 years and the minimum age is also 26. Moreover, the mean age of the respondents is 49 years old.

To sale their agricultural outputs specifically (teff), households must travel somewhere with a limed distance. On average, households travel 4.1 kilometers to reach the nearest markets and the maximum distance that the households travel is 6.5 kilometers. To the contrary, the minimum distance is 1kilometer.

Teff production is labor intensive activity. Therefore, households with higher numbers of family size have high labor share. As it seen from the tables, the average family size of the sample respondent is almost 4. The maximum family size of the respondents is 7 members and the minimum family size is only 2 members. Thus, imply that on average sample respondents have small family sizes.

Livestock size is also another important socio economic variable that shows the sample households endowment of cattle. Livestock endowment includes oxen, caws, horses, donkeys, sheep, goats, hens and mules. It is used as source of income through selling them and to carryout different activities. From the table mentioned above, there researcher depicts that; the average livestock size of the respondents is 6.3 tropical livestock unit. Moreover, the maximum livestock size of the sample respondent is 18 TLU and the minimum holding is 1.7 TLU.

Households take in to account the previous year market price of teff when they are interested to sale their output in the markets. The above mentioned table illustrate that, the previous year average market price of teff in quintals was 1803.56 birr. Besides the minimum price of teff was 1700 birr per quintals and the maximum price that household’s sale a quintals of teff was 1900 birr. There is significant difference among households with the sales of teff in quintals. On average, there are 33. 3 birr deviations.

Land is an important resource for all living things. Higher percentage of Land allocated to teff production enables to the household to surplus product. As shown from above table, the researcher depicts that land allocated for teff could be measured with hectares and on average; the sample households allocate 2.5 hectares of land for teff production. The minimum land allocated for teff production was 0.5 hectares and the maximum land size allocated for the teff production was 6 hectares.

C. Levels of commercialization

According to leavy and poulton (2007), households have three different levels of commercialization that operates as subsistence (non-commercial), semi-commercial and commercial.

Table 11: levels of commercialization of teff production for the respondents

Levels of commercialization	Frequency	Percentage
Commercial	35	15.91%
Semi-commercial	120	54.54%
Non- commercial(Subsistence)	65	29.54%
Totals	220	100 %

Source: survey of own computation 2018

The above table depicts that the levels of commercialization of sample households that participate in the teff production and selling activity are strongly vary across their levels. From the table 11, 54.54% of sample respondents are categorized under semi commercial levels, 29.54% of the sample households are categorized under non commercial levels (subsistence) and only 15.91% of the sample respondents are commercial one. Generally, from the table the researcher could conclude that on average the sample respondents in the study area are semi commercial one.

The levels of commercialization also vary across households based on sex and agro ecology zone. The following tables show that levels of commercialization based on sex and agro ecology zone.

Table 12: levels of commercialization of households based on sex

Sex of the households heads	Levels of commercialization		
	Commercial	semi commercial	Non commercial
Male	24(10.9%)	85 (38.63%)	48(21.81%)
Female	11(5.01%)	35 (15.91%)	17(7.73%)
Totals	35 (15.91%)	120(54.54%)	65(29.54%)

Source: survey of own computation 2018.

From the above tables, 71.63% of respondents are male households head. Of which, 10.9% of the sample respondents are commercial one, 38.63% are semi commercial and 21.81% are non commercial (subsistence). On the other hand, 28.37% of the sample respondents are female head. From the total female respondents, 5.01 % of respondents are commercial, 15.91% are semi commercial, and lastly7.73% of respondents are non commercial (subsistence). Generally commercial males’ heads covered 17.5% from the total male households (24 of 137) and female commercial heads (17.4%) from the total sample female respondent (11 of 65). this indicates that males are more commercial than females.

Table 13: levels of commercialization of households based on agro ecology zone.

Agro ecology zone	Levels of commercialization		
	Commercial	Semi commercial	Non commercial
Woyna dega	28(12.72%)	90(40.9%)	20 (9.09%)
Dega	2(0.9%)	17(7.7%)	23((10.45%)
Kola	5(2.27%)	13(5.94%)	22(10%)
Total	35 (15.91%)	120 (54.54%)	65(29.54%)

Source: Based on own survey data 2018

The above mentioned tables shows the levels of commercialization of teff of sample households that live in the three agro ecology zone of the study area. From 15.91% of total commercial households, 12.72% are found in woyna dega zone and the remaining 0.9% and 2.27 % of the commercial households are found in Daga and kola agro ecology zone respectively. This indicates dega zone is had the lowest share of commercialization.

The other level of commercialization of teff production was semi commercial. 54.54% of the respondents are semi commercialized one. Of which, 40.9% of the semi commercial households are found in woynadaga zone. Moreover, 7.7% and 5.94% of sample respondents under semi commercial levels are found or live in dega and kola zone of the study area respectively.

The third level of commercialization was non- commercial (subsistence). From 29.54% of total subsistence respondents, 9.09% of the sample respondents found in woyna dega zone, 10.45% of the respondent is found in dega zone and the remaining 10% are respondents are under kola zone. Generally, woyna dega zone was highly commercial as compare to the other two agro ecology zones.

D. Total factor productivity outcomes of teff commercialization

Priority aim of commercialization has been directly attached to household's welfare maximization through its positive effects on income, employment, education, health, consumption and other expenditure (Goitom, 2009). Likewise, sharp and Samuel (2007) measured welfare outcome of commercialization through land productivity, consumption expenditure and labor productivity. Moreover, they pointed out that farm productivity was considered as an immediate outcome that could be achieved by high involvement in the output market.

This study consider only factors productivity outcomes of teff output from other crop outputs and the factor production included fertilizer, pesticides, labor, land, oxen and special seeds. Moreover, it could be measured with the ratio of output commercialization index per input commercialization index. The interest was to examine the influence of total factor productivity outcomes on different levels of commercialization. Basically, levels of commercialization at household levels can be categorized in to three groups based on their selling of crop outputs. These are commercial (if households sold 50% and above), semi commercial (if households sell 26-50%) and subsistent (non commercial, if households sold less than 25%).

Table 14: TFP outcomes of teff production of sample households based on levels of commercialization

Levels of commercialization	Observation	Total factor productivity(TFP)	
		Mean	Std. dev
Commercial	35	3.2531576	1.0107803
Semi commercial	120	2.3683349	1.1816963
Subsistence (non commercial)	65	1.2135402	.61090929
Totals	220	2.1679128	1.2276129

Source: Based on own survey data 2018

One-way ANOVA test was applied to check the existence of significant factor productivity difference among households that operate under the three levels of commercialization. The ANOVA test revealed that there is statistically significant difference in factor productivity outcomes among households that operated in commercial, semi commercial and subsistence levels of commercialization. In this case null hypotheses that ANOVA holds is, there is equal mean among the groups and if it's not hold true, accept alternative hypotheses and reject the null. Based on table 14, the mean of total factor productivity outcomes that operate in the commercial, semi commercial and subsistence levels of commercialization is 3.25, 2.37 and 1.21 respectively. The average total factor productivity outcome of the total sample respondents is 2.167. Moreover, the overall significance of factor productivity outcomes of teff production can be checked with F value in the one way ANOVA (prob> F= 0.000). Thus, factor productivity outcomes are significant among the levels of commercialization at 1% levels of significant (see appendix H).

E. Factor that affect market participation

To analyze the factors that affect households' participation in the teff output market, multiple linear regression analysis was used. Households' participation in the teff market or commercialization of teff could be affected by both demographic and a socio economic variable as it was explained in the descriptive analysis. The dependent variable is market participation of households in

the teff market. It is a continuous variable that ranges between zero and one. Therefore, the researcher use censored Tobit regression model.

There are numbers of demographic and socio economic variable that affect households participation in the teff market. The factors includes; age, educational levels, access to market information, access to credit, access to extension service, access to training, participation in the off farm activity, livestock holding or endowment, family size, land size (land allocated for teff production), distance to the nearest market, market price of teff (previous year) and access to irrigation.

Table 15 Tobit estimate result of determinants of market participation

Maktpa	Coefficients	T	P>t	Marginal effects
OFFAM	-.1274909	-9.73	0.000	-.1274909
Lansize	.0356661	6.27	0.000	.0356661
Pyprice	.0003676	1.79	0.074	.0003676
Livsize	.0019229	0.92	0.358	.0019229
Fasize	-.009343	-1.60	0.112	-.009343
Mktinfo	.009247	0.72	0.469	.009247
Distance	-.0022117	-0.49	0.622	-.0022117
Accext	.0053734	0.40	0.687	.0053734
Training	.0069927	0.55	0.586	.0069927
Accrt	-.0398256	-2.85	0.005	-.0398256
Eduhh				
2	.0312838	-2.07	0.040	.0312838
3	-.0500824	-2.55	0.012	-.0500824
4	-.0216815	-0.71	0.481	-.0216815
5	-.0136166	-0.32	0.748	-.0136166
Agehh	.0003708	0.50	0.616	.0003708
_cons	-.3381207	-0.91	0.362	

Source: based on survey of own commutation

The above table (15) depicted the Tobit estimation of determinant of market participation of households in the red papper output market. The F value indicates that the overall significant of the model. Prob> chi2 = 0.000 indicate that the model was accurately predicted by the explanatory variables.

Moreover, the Tobit regression model shows that from 12 independent variables, five explanatory variables were statistically significantly at 1%, 5 % and 10% levels of significance. Of which, participation in the off farm activities (1%), land allocated for red papper (1%), last year price of red papper (10%), access to credit (5%) and education levels (read and write only at 5% and 1-4 grade levels at 5%) statistically significant .

➤ *Last year price of red papper:*

Last year market price of teff affect market participation of households in the red papper market positively and statistically significant at 10%. This implies that the higher last year market price leads the households to participate more in the red papper market. From the Tobit estimation, as last year price of red papper in the market increased by one birr ($\beta=0.003$), households participation in the market increased by 0.3%. This indicated that since price is incentives to household's to supply and sale more. Households more likely participate in the market as last year price of teff were higher. This finding is consistent with the fining of Edward (2013).

➤ *Access to credit:*

It was statistically significant and negatively associated with market participation of households in the teff market. Market participation of households with access to credit service from formal financial institution is 39% lower than those without access to credit service. This finding is inconsistent with the finding of Agwu et al (2013) that implies households with credit service from financial institution more likely participate in the market as compare to non user. Since credit service enhance the farmer to link with modern technologies (such as fertilizer, special seed and crop protection), to invest in modern machinery and overcome constraints of inputs supply. But accesses to credit service decrease market participation of households in the red papper market since households are reluctant to take credit service from low cash flow performance sector and fraud of uncertainty in the interest rate and repayment schedule.

➤ *Land size (% of land allocated for red papper):*

Land allocated for teff production was statistically significance at 1% and positively affect market participation of households in the red papper market. Higher Land size enhances households for surplus production through economies of scales and increase crop diversification (partly cash crop and partly food crops). Thus, market participation of households increased by 35.6 % as land allocated for teff increased by one hectare. This finding is consistent with the finding of (Edward, 2013, Chalachew et al, 2011 and Adam, 2009) that implies households with larger land allocated for

red papper able to produced marketable surplus and more likely participate in the market.

➤ *Participation in the off farm income activity:*

Participation in the off farm activities statistically significant at 1% and negatively affect market participation of household in the red papper market. Market Participation of households with participation in the off farm activities is 12.7% less than from the non participant. This is because income obtained from participation in the off farm activities is not invested in the farm technology and other farm improvement activities. Therefore, households who participate in the off farm activities less likely participate in the red papper market. This finding is inconsistent with the finding of (Edward, 2013) that implies participation in the off farm income activities increase the money base and this increases investment on agriculture that encourage productivity and sales.

➤ *Education level:*

Education levels of the household are a categorical variable with five categories and consider the first level as a baseline. Of which, level 2 (read and write only) and level 3(1-4 grade level) are statistically significant at 5% and negatively influence market participation of households. These indicates households with read and write only level and 1-4 grade levels less likely increase market participation of household as compare to illiterate households. This is because educated households mostly migrate to the nearest urban area that is employment is prevalent and divert their skill to off farm employment opportunity. This indicates households reduce dependency in the agriculture activity and limit market sale. Generally, households with read and write only and 1-4 grade level participate in the market 3.1% and 5% less than illiterate households .This finding is consistent with the finding of Atau and Elias (2015) .

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. *Summary and Conclusions*

Commercialization enhance the farm households maximize welfare, smooth consumption through increasing agricultural productivity, reduction of poverty, increase household income, and strength market linkage. It is also the prior development agenda and poverty reduction strategy of Ethiopia government to transform smallholder farmer from subsistence to profit maximizing (commercial).

This research addressed the determinants of commercialization of red papper and its factor productivity outcomes, the case of buie Woreda, Amahara Region, and Ethiopian. Particularly, the research analyzed the levels of commercialization of red papper production at household levels, examined the factor that affect household participation in the teff output market or commercialization and the influence factor productivity outcomes that operate at the different levels of commercialization.

The method of data collection technique applied in this research was structured questioners and the target populations were rural farm households that could produce teff outputs.

Basically primary data were collected through this tool. Furthermore, 220 sample respondents were selected from the three agro ecology zone .i.e Woyna daga, Dega and kola zone and stratified random sampling was adopted to select representative sample kebeles/ village and there are only 2 defected households during the data collection.

The study was analyzed by both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics was applied to analysis the levels of commercialization. There are three categories of levels of commercialization at the household levels. These are commercial, semi commercial and subsistence levels. Moreover, one way ANOVA test was used to examine factor productivity outcome that varies on different levels of commercialization. Accordingly, there was a significant difference in the factor productivity outcomes of teff production among the sample households that operate at the different levels of commercialization. This indicates that households with the higher TFP index participate in the teff output market more as compare to households with lower TFP index.

Basically, the descriptive analysis revealed, the average educational levels of the households in the studying area was read and write only categories. Moreover, male household heads were more educated than female heads. Regarding to religious status, households are almost (93.63%) Christian. The average age of the sample respondents in the study area was 49 years old and cultivate on average 2.5 hectares of land for teff production.

The descriptive analysis also depicts that the levels of commercialization of teff production in the study area is characterized as semi commercial level. On average, 54.54% of sample respondents are semi commercial, 15.91% of respondents are commercial one and the remaining 29.54% of the respondents are subsistence. Based on sex, male household heads are more commercial one as compare to female heads. Likewise, based on agro ecological zone, levels of commercialization was high in Woyna dega zone as compare to Kola and Degazone. Households in the dega agro ecological zone were almost subsistence or non commercial.

The censored Tobit regression result revealed that from the total 12 explanatory variables, only five variables are statistically significant at 1%,5% and 10% levels of significance and determine market participation of households. Of which, education level (read and write only and 1-4 grade level) , access to credit service and participation in the off farm activities negatively affect market participation of households in the teff market . To the contrary, land allocated to teff and last year market price of teff positively and significantly influences market participation of households.

Previous year market price of teff was significant and positively affects market participation of households. This is because price is an incentive for farm households to supply more output in the market. Likewise, Land allocated for teff (by hecters) also positively influence market participation of the household. This implies that larger land size enables the

households to produce diversified crop (cash and food crop) and attain surplus production through economies of scale.

To the contrary, access to credit service from the formal financial service negatively affects market participation of households in the teff market. This is because households are reluctant to take credit and afraid of uncertain interest rate and repayment schedule. Likewise, participation in the off farm income activities also negatively influence market participation of households. This is because income earned from participation in the off farm activities is not invested in farm technology and other farm improvement activities.

Finally, education levels (read and write only and 1-4 grade level) of households also negatively affect market participation of households. This is due to educated households mostly migrate to the urban area that employment is prevalent and divert the generated skill to off farm employment opportunity.

Generally, the levels of commercialization of teff producing rural farm households in the study area were lower. Even though levels of commercialization was lower, there were significant factor productivity difference among households at each levels

B. Policy Recommendations

Based on the finding obtained from the discussion, the following policy recommendation has been drawn.

The level of commercialization of teff production of households in the study area was semi commercial levels. This indicates that households produce half for consumption and half for sale. Thus, to achieve high welfare, reduce poverty and increase income, government should strongly support the rural farm household to transform from semi commercial to commercial level through creating market linkage and short term agricultural training .

Land allocated for teff was positively affect market participation of households. Teff is highly demanded and consumed cash and food crop particularly in the study area. Thus, there should be development of off farm activities because labor shift from farm to off farm activates and this increase availability of land. Moreover, government should consolidate fragmented farm structure and functioning land reform policy.

Previous year market price of teff also affects market participation of households positively. Therefore, government should control and monitor unnecessary intervention of broker or intermediary that benefit with the expense of farmers. Moreover, government price regulation policy should consider not only manufacturing good but also agricultural output to solve seasonal fluctuation in price.

Access to credit service from the formal financial institution negatively influences market participation of households. Therefore, financial institution should manage the interest rate and repayment schedule. Moreover,

awareness creation should be done to avoid reluctant behavior of households.

Participation on the off farm activities negatively affect market participation of households. Therefore, the concerned body should create awareness and provide training for households to invest the money obtained from participation in the off farm activity in to farm technology and other farm improvement activities.

Education levels of the household (read and write only and 1-4 grade level) negatively affect market participation of households. It is recommended that government or the concerned body should create sound environment to reduce migration of educated households to the urban area.

SUGGESTION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Determinants of commercialization of teff and its factor productivity outcome: the case of buie worreda , amahara region, Ethiopia . It is better to be done the case of Ethiopia, include the urban farmers and take account determinants of input commercialization.

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